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JGI

**SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER
 JAIN EVENING COLLEGE**

(Affiliated to Bengaluru City University)
 V V Puram Bengaluru 560004

In Association with IQAC, NAAC
 Organized
**INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
 ON**

Volume - 4
 Issue - 8
 (Special Issue, August 2023)

**RECENT ADVANCEMENT AND INNOVATION IN
 BUSINESS & MANAGEMENT & ITS
 CONTEMPORARY ISSUES IN SUSTAINABLE ECONOMICS
 "ICRAIMB 2023**

Date: 02 & 03 August 2023

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**International Conference Recent Advancement
and Innovation in Business & Management &
Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable
Economy “ICRAIBM 2023”
2nd & 3rd August 2023**

Publication Partner
**International Journal of Multidisciplinary
Research and Technology**

ABOUT COLLEGE – SRI BHAGAWAN MAHAVEER JAIN EVENING COLLEGE, AFFILIATED TO BENGALURU CITY UNIVERSITY, BENGALURU

Sri Bhagawan Mahaveer Jain Evening College is an esteemed educational institution known for its commitment to academic excellence, holistic development, and ethical values. Situated in Bengaluru, this college has been a beacon of knowledge and learning since its establishment.

Founded with the vision of imparting quality education rooted in Jain principles, SBMJEC strives to nurture students into well-rounded individuals who possess not only intellectual acumen but also a deep sense of social responsibility. The college offers a wide range of undergraduate and postgraduate programs across various disciplines, catering to the diverse interests and aspirations of its students.

At SBMJEC, education goes beyond textbooks and classrooms. The college emphasizes the importance of experiential learning, providing ample opportunities for students to engage in practical applications of their knowledge through internships, research projects, and community service initiatives. This holistic approach to education ensures that students not only acquire subject-specific expertise but also develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and interpersonal skills that are essential for success in the professional world.

The college boasts a highly qualified and dedicated faculty who are not only experts in their respective fields but also mentors and guides to the students. They foster an environment of intellectual curiosity, encouraging students to explore new ideas, challenge existing notions, and embrace lifelong learning.

Apart from academics, SBMJEC offers a vibrant campus life with a range of extracurricular activities, clubs, and student organizations. These provide students with opportunities to pursue their passions, develop leadership skills, and form lasting friendships.

With its state-of-the-art facilities, well-stocked library, advanced laboratories, and modern infrastructure, SBMJEC provides an ideal environment for students to thrive academically, intellectually, and personally.

SBMJEC stands as a prestigious institution that instills a sense of purpose, integrity, and excellence in its students. It equips them with the knowledge, skills, and values necessary to succeed in their chosen fields and make a positive impact on society.

ABOUT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE - ICRAIBM 2023

The conference aims to provide a platform for knowledge sharing between academic researchers and business practitioners in order to support transformative changes for addressing contemporary organizational challenges. Disruptive technologies and innovations are challenging businesses to rethink who they are, what they stand for, how they operate and how they could organize for the future. For successfully pivoting the business, organizations must nurture a culture that promotes constant transformation and understand that convergence in all spheres is absolutely critical when making transformations. Facing a complex future, leaders/managers increasingly need research-based information and evidence more than ever.

The academic research scenario in India is changing in light of the recent developments in educational reforms, especially with the implementation of NEP 2020, which seeks to transform higher education by focusing on skill-based education to meet the rapidly changing needs of the industry and the economy.

Towards this, the UGC has taken a new initiative to bring the industry and other professional expertise into the academic institutions by creating a new category of positions called Professor of Practice, through which industry experts will be brought in to play the role of faculty members in the Higher Education Institutions (Hei's). All these necessitate broader and deeper engagements between Hei's and industry

partners, wherein academia needs to build a consultative and collaborative approach to working with businesses and building programs that meet business needs.

In this context, the central theme of the conference is focused on making academic research more relevant to business organizations and bringing together suggestions to enhance the relevance of academic research to practice on a real-time basis.

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PROFESSOR, TISHK INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY

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KEYNOTE SPEAKERS: DAY 2

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VINAY BN

PROJECT PROGRAM MANAGEMENT SPECIALIST, NTT DATA

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MESSAGE BY THE CHAIRMAN & FOUNDER

DR. CHENRAJ ROYCHAND -JGI- JAIN GROUP OF INSTITUTION

I am honoured to address you all as we gather here today for the prestigious two-day International Conference organised by SBM Jain Evening college on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy." This event serves as a remarkable platform for professionals, academics, and visionaries from around the globe to converge and share their insights on the pressing matters that shape our world.

In an era defined by rapid change and evolving challenges, the importance of exploring the realms of business and management within the context of a sustainable economy cannot be overstated. Today, as we witness the interplay between innovation, entrepreneurship, and environmental consciousness, we must chart a course that not only maximizes economic growth but also ensures the well-being of our planet and its inhabitants.

Our distinguished speakers, renowned experts in their respective fields, will share their knowledge, expertise, and groundbreaking research, offering unique perspectives and insights. Their contributions will undoubtedly stimulate thought-provoking discussions, foster collaboration, and inspire innovative solutions that can drive us towards a more sustainable and prosperous future.

This conference is not just a mere gathering of minds but an opportunity to forge meaningful connections, build networks, and cultivate partnerships. As we engage in stimulating conversations, let us seize the chance to exchange ideas, challenge conventional wisdom, and uncover new approaches that can pave the way for transformative change.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the organizing committee, whose tireless efforts have brought us all together. Their dedication, passion, and meticulous planning have ensured the success of this conference, which promises to be a remarkable experience for all involved.

I would like to express my deepest appreciation to all the participants who have travelled from different corners of the globe to be here today. Your presence signifies your commitment to advancing knowledge, promoting sustainability, and shaping a better future for generations to come.

Let us embark on this journey of discovery, enlightenment, and collaboration. May the next two days be filled with thought-provoking discussions, insightful presentations, and meaningful connections. I have no doubt that the ideas and solutions generated during this conference will make a lasting impact on the world of business, management, and our sustainable economy. I wish you all a productive and rewarding conference.

MESSAGE BY THE PRINCIPAL

DR. K. M. MAHESH, PRINCIPAL SBM JAIN EVENING COLLEGE, BENGALURU & SYNDICATE MEMBER BENGALURU CITY UNIVERSITY

It is my utmost pleasure to extend a warm welcome to all of you to the prestigious International Conference on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy," hosted by SBMJEC. This two-day event, scheduled to take place on the 2nd and 3rd of August, promises to be a remarkable gathering of thought leaders, professionals, and academicians from across the globe.

As the Principal of SBMJEC, I am thrilled to witness the convergence of brilliant minds and passionate individuals who share a common goal: to explore, discuss, and shape the future of business and management within the realm of a sustainable economy. This conference offers a platform to exchange groundbreaking ideas, cutting-edge research findings, and innovative strategies that will propel us towards a more sustainable and prosperous world. In an era where businesses and organizations are increasingly called upon to balance profitability with social and environmental responsibility, the need for advancements and innovations in business and management practices becomes more pronounced.

During the next two days, our distinguished speakers, renowned experts in their respective fields, will take centre stage to share their expertise and experiences. Their presentations, panel discussions, and interactive sessions will provide an opportunity for profound learning, critical analysis, and collaborative problem-solving. Through these exchanges, we aim to identify and address the contemporary issues faced by businesses and management in the pursuit of sustainability.

I express my heartfelt gratitude to the conference conveners Dr. Lakshman K Associate professor & Head, Department of Management, SBM Jain Evening college & Mrs. Shruti MS, Assistant Professor & Head, Department of Commerce, SBM Jain Evening College, organizing committee, teaching staff & non-teaching staff, students whose unwavering commitment and meticulous planning have made this conference possible. Their dedication, foresight, and attention to detail ensure that this event is of the highest standard, offering a memorable and enriching experience for all attendees.

I would like to extend my sincere appreciation to each participant who has joined us for this conference. I am excited about the possibilities that lie ahead and the transformative discussions that will take place during this conference. Together, let us embrace the power of innovation, drive change, and pave the way for a more sustainable future.

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS FOR DAY 1 ICRAIBM 2023

Dr. Ramalakshmi

Professor Of MBA At Krupa Nidhi Group of Institutions
Bangalore

Dedicated and experienced college professor with over twenty years of experience serving as Associate Professor in MBA Department. Proficient in creating powerful curriculum in the fields of Mathematics, Statistics and Operations Research. Expert at working with students to successfully prepare them for personal and professional success in today's world. Knowledgeable and experienced in various educational philosophies, which best promote the overall experience of a student. A committed faculty member, passionate about working to further enhance the educational offerings of an institution.

Dr. Ghousia Khatoon

Professor & Head, Tishk International University
Iraq

She is currently working as Full Professor at the Department of Accounting, Banking and Finance, Tishk International University, Erbil, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. She has worked as an Associate Professor in Prince Sultan University and as an Assistant Professor in Princess Nourah University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. She has to her credit Bachelor's in Commerce, Master's in Commerce, Master's in Business Administration, Post Graduate Diploma in Management, Post Graduate Diploma in Financial Management, Diploma in Management and PhD in Venture Capital Finance (PhD Thesis evaluated by Australian Catholic University, Australia). She has more than two decades of experience in teaching and research. She has authored 18 books and published 38 research articles in the journals of repute including Scopus indexed journals and journals indexed in Web of Science such as WILEY, Inderscience Publishers, Taylor & Francis and MDPI. She is the recipient of Best Paper Award on 'Strategies for inclusive growth' at SBJIT, Bangalore, India and Distinguished teacher award from MTC Global. She is also the recipient of MTC Global Outstanding Researcher Award -2022. She has presented research papers in international conferences at China, Spain, Romania, Malaysia, UAE, Jordan and Iraq. She has chaired sessions and delivered keynote address in international conferences and reviewed papers for Springer, Information Sciences Letters (Scopus, Q2) and Eurasian Journal of management and Social Sciences. Her areas of Expertise include Green Finance, Start-Up Finance, FDI, Auditing, IFRS, Forensic Accounting, Financial Literacy, Fintech, Venture Capital, Environmental Accounting, Gender diversity and Corporate Performance.

KEYNOTE SPEAKERS FOR DAY 2 ICRAIBM 2023

(Dr.) Hemant Chittoo

Professor & Head, Department of Management, University of Technology, Mauritius

Professor Hemant Chittoo has more than 30 years' experience in different Tertiary Education Institutions in Mauritius and has been a visiting Faculty for Universities in UK and Australia. He is a Professor, Researcher, Consultant in the field of Management. He has led the School of Business, Management and Finance for 6 years and has been the Ag. Director General of the University of Technology, Mauritius for nearly 2 years, among other major functions he has held. He has managed several crisis situations successfully. He has provided consultancy services to the World Bank, the UNICEF, CIDA, CAFRAD, British American Tobacco, and a number of Companies in Mauritius including he has written 3 reports for the Government of Mauritius, several book chapters, more than 80 articles in refereed journals and some 50 conference papers. He has also been invited as keynote speaker in a number of international conferences. Leading education and strategy education at the University of Technology, Mauritius, Dr. Chittoo has participated in the formulation of the National Strategic Foresight Exercise 2050 for Mauritius and has been member of different National level Committees for the Government of Mauritius. He has insights into a number of sectors in Mauritius.

Mr. Vinay BN

Project Program Management Specialist, NTT Data

I'm Open Minded person and always open to learning new things. Always Humble to grow along with the company and soft-spoken and to the point. Take decisions quickly. Dedicated and experienced management specialist with over Fifteen years of experience serving as a Project Programme management Specialist in NTT Data Ltd, Bengaluru, Karnataka. Proficient in creating efficient and trending strategies for the department and to my career. Expert at working with team to successfully prepare them for personal and professional success in today's business world. Knowledgeable and experienced in various educational philosophies, which best promote the overall experience of a Project specialist. A committed &, passionate about working to further enhance the professional offerings to the modern business.

ABOUT CONFERENCE-BY-CONFERENCE CONVENORS

It is with great pleasure and enthusiasm that we extend a heartfelt welcome to all of you to the esteemed International Conference on "Recent Advancement and Innovation in Business & Management and Its Contemporary Issues in Sustainable Economy. "Organised by SBM Jain Evening College, Bengaluru 2nd August 2023 and 3rd August 2023. As the convenor's of this two-day International Conference, We are honoured to have the opportunity to bring together exceptional minds and passionate professionals from various corners of the world.

This conference serves as a vital platform for intellectual exchange, collaboration, and exploration of the pressing issues at the intersection of business, management, and sustainability. In an era defined by dynamic changes, disruptive technologies, and increasing environmental concerns, it is crucial for us to come together and foster a deeper understanding of the advancements and innovations that shape our ever-evolving landscape.

Over the next two days, we have curated an enriching program featuring distinguished speakers, experts, and researchers who will present their groundbreaking work, share valuable insights, and challenge conventional wisdom. Their contributions will encompass a broad range of topics, including sustainable business practices, corporate social responsibility, entrepreneurship, digital transformation, and emerging trends in the global economy.

As the convenor, We would like to express Our deepest gratitude to the organizing committee members, teaching staff, and non-teaching staff, our beloved students of SBM Jain evening college for their unwavering commitment, tireless efforts, and meticulous planning. Their dedication has ensured that this conference offers a seamless experience for all participants, allowing us to focus on the most critical issues at hand.

We also extend our sincere appreciation to each and every participant for your valuable presence and active involvement. Your contributions, whether through presentations, panel discussions, or fruitful conversations during the networking sessions, will undoubtedly shape the outcomes of this conference and inspire new avenues for research and practice.

Moreover, we encourage you to seize this occasion to foster connections, forge partnerships, and engage in meaningful collaborations that transcend geographical boundaries. The diverse backgrounds, expertise, and perspectives represented here offer a remarkable opportunity to build networks, share best practices, and collectively contribute to the sustainable development of our global community. Thank you and we wish you all a rewarding and successful conference.

Warm regards,

Dr. Lakshman K
Conference Convenor, Associate Professor & Head,
SBMJEC, Bengaluru

Mrs. Shruthi MS
Conference Convenor, Assistant Professor & Head,
SBMJEC, Bengaluru

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AN EVALUATION OF TRAINING PERFORMANCE – A CASE STUDY OF PRADHAN MANTRI KOUSHAL VIKAS YOJANA IN BAGALKOT DISTRICT

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ABSTRACT:

Training programs enhances the skills and knowledge of the trainees. The rapidly changing global industrial scenario and technological advancements affects the training ecosystem periodical evaluation or assessment of training programs reveals the training program efficiency. In this backdrop, the study was undertaken with the basic purpose of reviewing the Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in terms of its performance in Bagalkot District, Karnataka State. With a sample of 200 male and female beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal vikas Yojana were selected for this study. To fulfill the aims of this study the author had identified dependent and independent variables and they were analyzed using appropriate statistical tools and techniques. The outcomes of the study will help the concerned people or authority to get more insights and background about the training effectiveness. While addressing the shortfalls, the study observations may contribute positively for the improvement of training program

KEY WORDS: training, PMKVY, performance, upscaling, infrastructure, pedagogy, skills, skill development, employability,

INTRODUCTION:

Within shorter period of time India is elevated to fifth position from tenth position in world strongest economy rankings. The journey was full of thrones and the threats like inflation, Corona, world economic slow down and melting of foreign reserves didn't stop India to become economically powerful country. The ambitious projects like Digital India, Make in India, Infrastructure development, road, railway and aviation development programs have created ample of employment opportunities. Along with these gigantic projects, multinational companies expansion strategies and India being most market potential country for FMCG, Electronic goods, Agricultural products, pharmaceutical products, Automobile industries, Telecommunication services and the stretching of FDI limits had welcome the companies with red carpet.

Whereas India with its poor skilled youth were unable to grab these golden opportunities. But still long time is waiting to utilize these offers. Post independence Central and state governments have put their efforts to improve the skill sets of the youth. Skill development programs and vocational training programs in the country have failed to increase the percentage of skilled labours and candidates across the country due to the improper design and implementation several programs. Now from 2015 to till, Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana a typical kind of training program is providing training programs in various job roles. Though the structure of training program is promising but the desired performance was not seen due to various factors.

This paper aims to measure the rate of skills acquisitions and determine the perception of the Trainees or Beneficiaries and to assess the Training performance of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District. The success of the training program is dependent on its major components and proper implementation. This study has identified the dependent and independent variables, which will help in understanding the relationship and importance of these variables.

Skill acquisition, training infrastructure and training pedagogies are the prime parts of any training program, which can be used as indicators of training performance. Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana encompasses more on training infrastructure, that's the reason the training centres and training partners were selected wisely. The training pedagogy is also as per the contemporary industry norms but still needs improvement. The perception of trainees or

beneficiaries towards skill acquisition needs to be collected and reviewed. This paper makes sincere effort to bringout the ground realities of this training program.

REVIEW OF LITRATURE:

Khan, and Khan (2011): This paper concentrates on Training and development issues. The methods of training, training content and execution part of the training and its implications on overall organization performance. The author proposes that the effective training can be achieved by proper structure and scientific development of the skill development programs. the major purpose of this study was to identify how skill enhancing exercises will boost the employee performance in the organization. the data was collected and processed through descriptive statistics and parametric tests were conducted. Both primary and secondary data were used to analyse the results. the study concluded that, the prominent training method such as on the job training plays an important role in employee performance and also it is time and cost effective method.

Kumar (2018) : This paper highlighted about the skill development programs under skill india mission and Make in India program. The popular skill development programs like Pradhan Mantri Kaushal Vikas Yojana, and Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana and their contribution in transforming Indian youth to Industry fit and employable were discussed. The paper with an important aim of understanding skill development programs and skill upgradation atmosphere in India. the leading training programs namely PMKVY, DDU-GKY (Deen Dayal Upadhyaya Gramin Kaushal Yojana), STEP (Support to Training and Employment Programme for Women), PMMY (Pradhan Mantri Mudra Yojana). were subject of the paper.

Misra (2015) : This paper focused on determining the rate of success of the goal i.e by 2022 mobilising cross together youth with fulpledge skills and competences. The paper aimed at investigating the training programs organized by NSDC and their efficacy level. The author was keen to observe the NSDC functioning with special reference to the skill development programs and their impact on employment and entrepreneurial activities in the country. The revamping of skill development programs and current frameworks of training programs were logically studies. The present industry environment and the threats posed on training programs are the hinderence for achieving the desired targets of the Authority.

Aggarwal (2016) : This paper highlighte on contemporary issues in skill development in India and problems faced by the skill development initiatives in India and strategic solutions for these issues and threats. the author meticulously observed the various elements like misalignment of requirements and availability of skilled human resources, locational disadvantages, training programs for women in India. the paper thrown light on the continues efforts of state and central government and private agencies in enhancing the skill enhancements and its contribution to the dveloping economy of the country.

Devi (2017) : This paper aimed at evaluating the ecosystem of skill development in India and the initiatives made in terms of programmes and policies that foster skill development. The study's primary goal was to make recommendations for a practical and structural response to the issue of India's existing and future workforce's severe shortage of critical skills and to be aware of the difficulties in skill development. The study looked at a number of variables, including national skill development and entrepreneurship policies. According to the national skill development mission and the skill India campaign, the notion of skill development has received widespread recognition, and several programmes and policies are being developed to introduce it not only in urban but also in rural areas.

Amegayibor (2021) : This paper concentrated on demographic factors influence on employee performance in Ghana Country. The important demographic factors like age, income, gender and occupation etc were considered for this interesting study. the author made a sincere attempt to measure the significance of the demographic factors like age and education on employee performance. This study determined the reason for absenteeism in the organization. From the findings it is crystal clear that age and department were the major reasons behind the continuous absenteeism in the organization. The other demographic factors were also studied and quantified in the process of ascertaining the employee performance in the organization.

Kanchan & Varshney (2015) ; This paper made an attempt to explore the skill development initiation and efforts, their impact on policy making and administrations in India. The paper was on the basis of exploratory study and existing literature were used to analyse the skill development scenario, the study revealed that more than 80% of Rural and Urban youth and working classes are lacking formal training and resulted in poor skill sets which is troubling them to focus on their jobs and it is affecting their job performance.

Bello et al (2013) ‘ This paper reviewed the significance of ICT in vocational and technical skill enhancements. A powerful country can be built only when the education and skill based training programs contribute to the growth. Now days the focus on employability skills are gaining more weightage and there is a requirement of upskilling the youth and workforce. The ancient and formal training programs are not enough to meet the expectations of present industries and job market. The applications of technology in all fields are preferring those candidates who are technically sound. The existing workforce and you may be able to handle the jobs but handling the jobs more effectively and efficiently candidates should possess the technical skills. Combination of several skills only get the job opportunities otherwise it will lead to unemployment problems in the country.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

Government of India launched several skill development programs; Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana is one among them. This PMKVY training program with its unique components attracted a large number of youths. To mobilize crores together youth for supplying to the industries is a Herculean job. The equations and formulae for the success of the industries and business are drastically changing. To meet these expectations and benchmarking MSME of India introduced PMKVY in 2015. After its inception, during these 8 years it has trained a large number of youths. Now it's right time to evaluate this training program performance, that's the reason behind choosing this research problem. It's an attempt to analyse and assess PMKVY .

OBJECTIVES:

1. To measure the Skills acquired by the Trainees or Beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District
2. To ascertain the perception of the Trainees or Beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District
3. To assess the Training performance of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

Figure: Conceptual Model of the study

This study comprises of dependent and independent variables. The above figure shows that, Skill acquisitions, Training Pedagogy and Training Infrastructure are the independent variables and the Training Performance is the Dependent variable. the study was conducted to establish the relationship among these variables. Which helps in determining the significance of these elements in a training Program.

Data Collection Methods

Secondary Data: Research Journals, Government department websites, thesis, dissertations, Magazines and Newspapers were used to gather information about Training and Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana.

Primary Data Sources : Structured questionnaire with interview method is adopted to collect first hand information.

Research Design: Exploratory and Descriptive Research Designs were used for this study. Both research designs helped in stating the research problem and analyzing the results.

Sample Size: 200 PMKVY Trainees and beneficiaries from Bagalkot District

Sampling Method: Random Sampling Method

Sample frame: Trainees list provided by various Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Kendra Bagalkot District

Sample Element: Beneficiaries and Trainees of Pradhan Mantri Koushal Vikas Yojana in Bagalkot District.

Sample Units: Bagalkot. Badami, Hungund, Bilagi, Mudhol, Jamakhandi, Teradal, Banahatti and Rabakavi, Guledgudda of Bagalkot District.

Sample Extent: Bagalkot District only

Research Instrument: A structured questionnaire with close ended questions were drafted and Likert scale, Dichotomous, Multiple questions were used to gather the information from the respondents.

Need for the Study: Training programs are the essential part of Human Resource Development. Training adds value to the existing performance of the Human resources. Skill enhancement and knowledge upgradation is possible through periodical training programs.

The framework of the training programs plays a vital role in transformation of a person to skilled and capable human resource. Continuous improvement in the framework will help in increasing the training performance, keeping this in mind the study on evaluation of training performance of PMKVY was selected. This study will contribute to the existing knowledge base.

Limitations of the Study

- The study is confined to Bagalkot District only
- Time and Cost were the major constraints for this study
- The selected sample is small as compared to the population.

ANALYSIS & FINDINGS:

Hypothesis of the Study

1. H1: There is a significant influence of Training Infrastructure on Training performance

Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	SA → TP	0.607	.402	133.246		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Training Infrastructure provided as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Training Infrastructure provided in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b=0.607, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Training Infrastructure provided, moreover the $R^2 = 0.402$ depicts that the model explains 40% of the variance in Respondents Training performance.

2. H1: There is a significant influence of Training Pedagogy on Training performance
 Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	TPG → TP	0.755	.628	334.338		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Training Pedagogy provided as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Training Pedagogy provided in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b=0.755, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Training Pedagogy provided, moreover the $R^2 = 0.628$ depicts that the model explains 62% of the variance in Respondents Training performance.

3. H1: There is a significant influence of Skill acquisition on Training performance
 Table shows the summary of findings

Hypothesis	Regression weights	Beta Coefficient	R ²	F	t-value	p-value	Hypothesis Supported
H1	TI → TP	0.686	.434	162.007		0.000	yes

Analysis: The hypothesis tests if Skill acquisition as significant impact on Respondents Training performance, the dependent variable Respondents Training performance was regressed on predicting variable, $F(1,198), p < 0.001$, which indicates that the Skill acquisition in shaping Respondents Training performance ($b=0.686, p > 0.001$). These results clearly direct the positive effect of Skill acquisition, moreover the $R^2 = 0.434$ depicts that the model explains 43% of the variance in Respondents Training performance

CONCLUSION:

The study can be concluded that, The Skill acquisitions are having significant effect on the training performance. Thus PMKVY training policy makers can concentrate on this skill acquisition aspect and can be reformed by taking necessary actions. The second hypothesis training pedagogy is also having significant impact on training performance. PMKVY is a well structured training program and the important factor training pedagogy can be updated periodically and advanced techniques, methods can be included in the curriculum. The third variable Training infrastructure is also significantly influences the training programs, PMKVY follows strict regulations in selecting training partners and training centres with special reference to training infrastructure, till there is scope for continues improvement of training infrastructure as and when the trainees desires.

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